

Chemistry of Benzoquinolines. Part I

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New evidences are presented to show that 2,4-dimethylbenzoquinoline, prepared by Combes' reaction from β -naphthylamine and acetyl acetone, is 6,7-benzoquinoline having a linear structure.

The Doebner-Miller and the Combes reactions are of general applicability for the synthesis of quinoline derivatives. Both the methods provide the same angular compound¹ (I) from α -naphthylamine. β -Naphthylamine, however, yields two different products by the above methods. Thus Reed² by the Doebner-Miller reaction obtained from β -naphthylamine, paraldehyde, and acetone a base melting at 126-27°. The Combes reaction between β -naphthylamine and acetylacetone is reported^{3,4} to yield a base melting at 66-67°.

Johnson and Mathews⁵ have suggested that structure (II) would correctly represent Reed's base (m.p. 126-27°). For the purpose of elucidating the structure of Combes' base (m.p. 66-67°), these workers studied its absorption spectrum and compared with that of anthracene. They found a close similarity between the absorption spectra of these two substances. They oxidised Combes' base by potassium dichromate to the corresponding quinone, which had absorption spectrum similar to that of anthraquinone. On these and other grounds, they proposed that Combes' base had the linear structure (IV). They have further postulated that the anil (III), obtained by the condensation of β -naphthylamine and acetylacetone, undergoes an unusual cyclisation at the 3-position to furnish this linear base (IV). They assigned structure (V) to the quinone. The above authors have named (IV) as 2,4-dimethylbenzo (g) quinoline, but a more appropriate name would be 2,4-dimethyl-6,7-benzoquinoline.

Since oxidation of compound (IV) had earlier failed to provide any product, which would directly indicate its linear structure, we decided to eliminate the methyl group at the 2-position and thus to obtain the known 4-methyl derivative (XIII), synthesised by Johnson *et al*⁵. This scheme was based on the assumption that the 2-methyl group in (IV) would be more reactive (as in 2,4-dimethylpyridine and 2,4-dimethylquinoline) and would readily react with benzaldehyde to provide the styryl base (X). Similarly, base (IV) with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde would provide (XI). The styryl compound (X or XI), on oxidation by potassium permanganate, was expected to yield the 4-methyl-2-carboxylic acid (XII), which on decarboxylation would furnish (XIII).

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 210.

2. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1887, **35**, 248.

3. Hollins, "Synthesis of Nitrogen Ring Compounds", D. Van Nostrand Company, New York, N.Y., 1924, pp. 266-70.

4. Combes, *Compt. rend.*, 1888, **106**, 1536.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 566.

The condensation of benzaldehyde with base (IV), however, followed a different pattern. This was first realised when the acid, obtained by oxidation of the styryl compound, failed to respond to a positive colour test with ferrous sulphate, indicating absence of a carboxyl group in the α -position. This was confirmed when the final product after decarboxylation was found to be identical with the 2-methyl-base (IX) and not the expected compound (XIII). Compound (IX) has been given different names [α -anthrapyridine, 2-methylbenzo (g) quinoline], but it would be more appropriate to call it 2-methyl-6,7-benzoquinoline. It is a known compound and its synthesis by Lindner and Stauffer⁶ shows that it has a linear structure. Thus the structure of the base (IV), proposed by Johnson and Mathews¹ for Combes' base, appears confirmed. It was thus fully established that the benzaldehyde had condensed with the methyl group at the 4-position affording (VI) and with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, the product was (VII). This indicates that the 4-methyl group is more reactive, a fact quite contrary to our expectation. It further appears that this unusual reactivity of the methyl group at the 4-position cannot be correlated with the electron densities at the 2- and 4-positions, as has been done in other cases, because such a calculation does not seem to have been made in the case of base (IV). It also means that instead of the expected 4-methyl-2-carboxylic acid (XII), the oxidation product of the styryl derivative is 2-methyl-4-carboxylic acid (VIII).

 (I: $R=R_1=Me$)

 (II: $R=R_1=Me$)

(III)

(V)

IV : $R=R_1=Me$.

VI : $R=Me$; $R_1=CH=CH.Ph$.

VII : $R=Me$; $R_1=-CH=CH.C_6H_4NO_2$.

VIII : $R=Me$; $R_1=-COOH$.

IX : $R=Me$; $R_1=H$.

X : $R=-CH=CH.Ph$; $R_1=Me$.

XI : $R=-CH=CH.C_6H_4NO_2$; $R_1=Me$.

XII : $R=-COOH$; $R_1=Me$.

XIII : $R=H$; $R_1=Me$.

A variety of methods was tried for the preparation of compounds (VI) and (VII). The condensation did not proceed smoothly either in presence of zinc chloride or refluxing acetic anhydride. In both cases only intractable oils or mixtures of solids were obtained. Although some of these were separated and purified, these were not further investigated. Another solvent tried was ethylene glycol, which also failed to provide the styryl derivative. The desired condensation was ultimately achieved by using a water separator, iodine as catalyst, and toluene as the solvent. On long refluxing under these conditions, the condensation was effected, furnishing a pure product in fairly good yield.

The oxidation failed to take place when the styryl base (VI or VII) was dissolved either in benzene or ethanol and heated with aqueous potassium permanganate. The right condition for effecting oxidation, as found, consisted in dissolving the styryl derivative (VI or VII) in cold acetone and treating this solution with finely powdered KMnO_4 , affording the acid (VIII) in good yield. Stachlin⁷ and Etienne and Stachlin⁸ have described the preparation of the acid (VIII) from benzo-isatin and acetone, melting at $327-29^\circ$. This melting point appears to be rather high from structural considerations. We have, however, found that compound (VIII) melts at $196-97^\circ$ with decomposition (evolution of CO_2), which appears to be in accord with its structure.

Decarboxylation of the acid (VIII) proceeded quite smoothly when a trace of copper powder was used as a catalyst. It was, however, found that complete decarboxylation was not possible without the use of a catalyst. Thus 2-methyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (IX) was easily obtained from the acid (VIII).

An improved method of preparation of 2,4-dimethyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (IV) has been described in which a much smaller quantity of sodium hydroxide is needed for liberating the free base from its insoluble sulphate. Besides this, as the sulphate is filtered and washed, the base obtained has no chance of contamination with any soluble impurities. Base (VI) melts at $90-92^\circ$ (Johnson and Mathews' report its m.p. as $91-93^\circ$). The melting point of Combes' base has been reported as $66-67^\circ$, which is probably the low-melting form, for which the above workers have reported its m.p. as $71-72^\circ$.

*EXPERIMENTAL

2,4-Dimethyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (IV) was prepared according to Johnson and Mathews' with some modification. The product from the condensation of β -naphthylamine and acetylacetone was purified by crystallisation from petroleum (b.p. $60-80^\circ$). This was cyclised by adding it portionwise to H_2SO_4 (cold, conc.) and then heating at 60° for 2 min. The hot solution was quickly cooled in ice and poured over crushed ice; the mixture was stirred and to it ice-cold water added. The yellow sulphate of 2,4-dimethyl-6,7-benzoquinoline settled down. This was filtered, washed, and suspended in water. The

⁷ *Compt. rend.*, 1951, 233, 262.

⁸ *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1954, 748.

*All m.p.s are uncorrected.

free base was obtained as a brown oil on addition of a moderately strong solution of NaOH to the suspension. The base was extracted with ether, washed with water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). The ether was distilled and the residue recrystallised from petroleum (b.p. 60-80°, charcoal). It melted sharply at 90-92° (Johnson and Mathews' report m.p. 91-93°).

The *picrate* was obtained by adding a saturated solution of picric acid in benzene to a solution of the base in benzene. It formed yellow silky needles from acetic acid, m.p. 264-65° (decomp.) (introduced in the bath at 250° following Johnson and Mathews' who report its m.p. as 271-73°). (Found: N, 12.85. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7\text{N}_4$ requires N, 12.39%).

2-Methyl-4-styryl-6,7-benzoquinoline (VI).—To the preceding base (IV) (2.06 g., 1*M*), dissolved in dry toluene (50 ml), were added freshly distilled benzaldehyde (1.06 g., 1*M*) and a trace of iodine. The mixture was refluxed for 4 hr. using a water separator to remove the water (ca. 0.3 ml) formed during the condensation. The solution was allowed to cool when a small quantity of reddish crystals of the iodine complex separated. This was filtered and the filtrate concentrated to a small volume (15 ml). On cooling, this deposited yellow rods (2 g.). It was recrystallised from ethanol (charcoal), m.p. 168-69°. (Found: N, 4.70. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}$ requires N, 4.75%).

2-Methyl-4-(3'-nitrostyryl)-6,7-benzoquinoline (VII).—To the base (IV) (2.06 g., 1*M*), taken in a r.b. flask and dissolved in dry toluene (50 ml), was added *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1.51 g., 1*M*). The mixture was refluxed similarly as above for 24 hr., concentrated to a small volume (ca. 15 ml), and allowed to stand overnight, when it deposited deep yellow, rod-like crystals (2.23 g.). It was recrystallised from toluene (charcoal), m.p. 186°. (Found: N, 8.70. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 8.88%).

2-Methyl-6,7-benzoquinoline-4-carboxylic Acid (VIII).—*2-Methyl-4-(3'-nitrostyryl)-6,7-benzoquinoline* (3.4 g.) was dissolved in acetone (400 ml) by thorough stirring and the solution was cooled below 0° (ice-salt bath). Finely powdered KMnO_4 (7.0 g.) was added portionwise to this solution with rapid stirring. The addition was completed during 30 min. The stirring was continued for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The mixture was then rapidly warmed to 60° on a water bath, cooled, and filtered. The solid obtained was washed with acetone, extracted with hot water (3 × 60 ml), and filtered. The combined filtrate (180 ml) was allowed to cool, acidified with excess HCl (conc.), and left overnight, when a yellow crystalline solid was deposited. This was filtered, dried, and extracted with ether (3 × 50 ml) to remove the easily soluble *m*-nitrobenzoic acid. The residue (2.04 g.) was crystallised from ethanol and petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) in light orange crystals, m.p. 196-97° (lit.^{7b} m.p. 327-29°). (Found: C, 73.84; H, 5.47; N, 5.43. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}$. $\frac{1}{2}$ H_2O requires C, 73.15; H, 4.88; N, 5.69%).

2-Methyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (IX).—The preceding acid (VIII) (0.5 g.) was mixed thoroughly with a trace of copper bronze powder and heated in a metal bath at 205-10° for about 2 min. The whole mass slowly melted with evolution of CO_2 and the magma was further heated *in vacuo*. The whole mass melted completely with brisk evolution of CO_2 . The bath temperature was also raised and at 280°, a yellow substance sublimed, forming a deposit at the cooler regions of the distilling tube (receiver). The tube was allowed to cool

and the yellow deposit was scraped out and collected (0.1 g.); m.p. 127-28° (lit.⁶ m.p. 129°). 2-*Methyl-6-benzoquinoline hydrochloride* from ethanol and benzene, m.p. 198-99° (lit.⁶ m.p. 200°). 2-*Methyl-6,7-benzoquinoline picrate* from ethanol, m.p. 248° (decomp.) (lit.⁶ m.p. 216°).

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